

A CASE REPORT OF NON-SURGICAL TREATMENT OF EAGLES SYNDROME

Gamba I.P.¹, Buabeng A.R.¹, Pupilampu P.¹, Ayiwah N.F.¹, Anim J.A.²

¹ College of Health and Well-Being, Oral Health Department

² Kintampo Health Research Centre

Corresponding Author. Dr Israel Patkuan Gamba¹, gabbiesgh@gmail.com, 0249707112,

ABSTRACT

This is a case report of Eagle's syndrome, a rare condition of elongation of the styloid process and calcification of the stylohyoid ligament.

In this case report, we discuss a 56-year-old male patient who visited the Oral Health Training and Service Center of the College of Health and Well-Being, presented with a left sided facial pain radiating to the ipsilateral ear, dysphagia, blocked nostrils, pain during rotation of neck to the left side and slight pain on mouth opening. A confirmed diagnosis was made radiologically via a three-dimensional volume-rendering Computed Tomography (CT) scan which is the most valuable diagnostic tool. The CT scan provided a far better radiological image of the findings allowing the length of both styloid processes and stylohyoid ligaments to be measured and its relationship to the adjacent anatomical structures evaluated. The syndrome can be managed surgically or conservatively. Nonetheless, this report presents a case of Eagle's syndrome that was managed conservatively.

INTRODUCTION

Eagles syndrome (ES) is a rare¹ symptomatic condition resulting from elongation of the styloid process or calcification of the styloid ligament². Though Watt Eagle defined the clinical syndrome in 1937³, it was first described in 1652 by Italian surgeon Pietro Marchetti¹. Eagle concluded that an adult is considered to have an abnormal styloid process if its length is more than 25mm. He classified the syndrome into two forms: the classic type and the carotid artery type, with the classic type presenting with symptoms such as a foreign body sensation in the throat, referred pain to the ear, and dysphagia and the carotid type showing symptoms such as migraines, and neurological symptoms, caused by irritation of the sympathetic nerve plexus associated with the artery⁴. Invariably, symptoms may present diversely depending on the degree of mineralization of the ligament, the length and width of the process and its angulation or curvature. Significant among the symptoms are headache, facial pain, sore throat, pain and difficulty in swallowing and foreign body sensation in pharynx; in rare cases, there could be obvious changes in voice and alteration in taste perception³.

Clinical diagnosis can be made via bimanual digital palpation of the styloid process in the tonsillar fossa, which worsens the pain during physical examination. In addition, diagnosis is highly suggestive when symptoms are alleviated after injection of an anesthetic solution into the tonsillar fossa⁵. Eagle syndrome can be managed conservatively or surgically but in most cases, surgical removal of the elongated styloid process is done.

Pharmacologically, its management might include neuroleptics, vasodilators, anti-histamines, anti-depressants, anti-epileptics and tranquilizers as a form of supportive therapy with various benefits of outcomes reported⁶. In this case report, the patient preferred conservative management and a significant treatment effect was observed. The case is reported as follows.

CASE REPORT

A 56-year-old male patient who visited the Oral Health Training and Service Center of the College of Health and

Well-Being, presented with a left sided facial pain of a month's duration. The pain was dull in nature, radiated to the left ear, there was associated dysphagia and blocked nostrils which progressively worsened over the period. His past medical history included a previous hospitalization about 5 years earlier due to a road traffic accident that involved the cervical spine which had rendered him paralyzed for some months, with no past history of dental visit. Patient was a known hypertensive and on medication. He was being managed by a physician who put him on analgesics and antibiotics, which did not relieve the pain and he was asked to see a dentist.

Upon extra oral examination, there was tenderness around the left side of the neck, and the mastoid region, which was worsened when he turned the neck to the left. Intra oral examination elicited tenderness upon palpation of the left lateral tonsillar fossa and retained root of the lower left second premolar. Lateral and Posterior Anterior radiographs of skull (Figure 1 and Figure 2 respectively) showed some level of ossification of the styloid ligament, which was not as obvious as the serial axial CT scan of the head and neck (up to C5) with 3D reformatted images (Figure 3). The CT showed bilateral elongated styloid process extending from the base of the skull anterolaterally and caudally just superior to the hyoid bone and heavily ossified styloid ligament (with the left markedly ossified compared to the right). The elongated left styloid process measured about 92mm while that of the right measured about 49mm. Laboratory investigations showed no significant findings except a raised lymphocyte count (46.8%) which was however not grossly abnormal.

The patient was diagnosed of Eagles syndrome based on the clinical and imaging findings. The relevant pathophysiology was explained to the patient and discussions centered on probable surgery, which the patient refused. Due to the severity of the pain a posterior superior alveolar and inferior alveolar nerve block with 2% Lidocaine (1:100,000) was performed (to confirm diagnosis and relieve pain) and complemented with some oral medications. Prescription of Tab Dexamethasone 8mg stat and 4mg twice daily for 24hours, Tab Diazepam 5mg nocte for 5days and Tab Tramadol 50mg twice daily for 7days was given.

Figure 1: Lateral view of the skull (Left)

Figure 2: Posterior Anterior view of skull

Figure 3: CT-Scan of the skull and neck

The symptoms gradually improved following the administration of the oral medications and injection after 3 weeks with the Visual Analog Scale for pain (VAS Pain) score reduced from the initial 8 (very severe) to 4 (moderate pain). However, review after 3 months showed tremendous relief in the pain after taking in the medications with VAS of 1 (no pain).

The team has discussed with an Oral and Maxillofacial surgeon and the patient intimated that he might consider a surgical procedure should the pain recur.

DISCUSSION

During embryogenesis, the Reichert cartilage of the second branchial arch gives rise to the styloid apparatus. As the fetus develops, the styloid apparatus gives rise to the styloid process (SP), ligament, and the small horn of the hyoid bone⁷.

The styloid process, an elongated tapered projection of the temporal bone, which anatomically lies between the internal and external carotid arteries, laterally to the tonsillar fossa and anterior to the mastoid process, a pyramidal bony projection from the posterior section of the temporal bone. The styloglossal, stylohyoid, and stylopharyngeous are the muscles that originate from the styloid process. The styloid and the stylohyoid ligaments are also attached to the styloid process^{4,8}.

The pathogenesis of the Eagles syndrome remains

debatable. According to Jain et al⁹ the ossification of the stylohyoid ligament is a congenital anomaly and thus may be due to an embryological phenomenon.

Moon et al⁴ also explained that the syndrome stems from various theories such as: 1) proliferation of granulation tissues compressing the surrounding areas leading to presentation of symptoms prior to a history of trauma leading to fracture of the styloid process; 2) inflammation of the tendinous part of the stylohyoid insertion (insertion tendonitis); 3) post-tonsillectomy scarring (with involvement of cranial nerves V, VII, IX, and X) leading to irritation of the mucosa of the pharynx; 4) the theory of irritation of the sympathetic nerves surrounding the carotid vessels; and 5) compression of the nerves such as the mandibular branch of the trigeminal, glossopharyngeal nerve, or the chorda tympani.

With a female dominance, the incidence of Eagles syndrome is reported to be about 4% of the general population, but of these, only about 0.16% present with symptoms that are attributable to elongation, mostly in persons aged 30 years and above¹⁰. Diagnosis of the syndrome could be missed as it presents with symptoms similar to temporomandibular disorders (TMD), aerodigestive tract malignancies, dental malocclusion and hyoid bursitis and neuralgia so a need for these conditions to be excluded before making a definitive diagnosis of Eagles syndrome. It presents with a variety of symptoms such as earache, odynophagia, dysphagia, specific cervical pain, foreign body sensation and pain due to rotation of the neck⁸.

Eagles syndrome is diagnosed by taking a good clinical history, doing adequate physical examination and conducting an appropriate radiographic investigation. With palpation of the tonsillar fossa producing characteristic pain⁴. Though currently the gold standard for diagnosing Eagles syndrome is CT scan¹¹, skull radiographs such as lateral cephalometric, Panoramic and Towne's projections can also be useful⁴.

Lidocaine infiltration test aids in diagnosis, as the symptoms are relieved after the anesthesia is injected into the tonsillar fossa³. With intra and extra oral approaches surgical removal of the elongated styloid process can be done. However, reports are being made of recurrence of symptoms post-operatively, questioning the benefit of surgical approach⁹. In this case, we planned a pharmacological form of management.

CONCLUSION

Eagle's syndrome should be considered when a patient complains of recurrent neck pains and TMJ symptoms. The condition can be diagnosed via a careful history, examination and plain radiographs or CT scan of the neck and skull to localize the pathological styloid process and ligament. Though surgical treatment is preferable treatment option, in this case a non-surgical approach in the management of eagle's syndrome achieved satisfactory results.

REFERENCES

1. Fusco DJ, Asteraki S, Spetzler RF. Eagle's syndrome: embryology, anatomy, and clinical management. *Acta neurochirurgica*. 2012;154(7):1119-26.
2. Kapoor V, Jindal G, Garg S. Eagle's syndrome: A New surgical technique for styloïdectomy. *Journal of maxillofacial and oral surgery*. 2015;14(1):360-5.
3. Han MK, Do Wan Kim JYY. Non surgical treatment of Eagle's syndrome-a case report. *The Korean journal of pain*. 2013;26(2):169.
4. Moon C-S, Lee B-S, Kwon Y-D, Choi B-J, Lee J-W, Lee H-W, et al. Eagle's syndrome: a case report. *Journal of the Korean Association of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgeons*. 2014;40(1):43-7.
5. Baharudin A, Rohaida I, Khairudin A. Transoral surgical resection of bilateral styloid processes elongation (Eagle's syndrome). *Acta Informatica Medica*. 2012;20(2):133.
6. Taheri A, Firouzi-Marani S, Khoshbin M. Nonsurgical treatment of stylohyoid (Eagle) syndrome: a case report. *Journal of the Korean Association of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgeons*. 2014;40(5):246-9.
7. Yasmeen Ahamed S, Laliytha B, Sivaraman S, Ambiga P, Dineshshankar J, Sudhaa M. Eagle's syndrome-Masquerading as ear pain: Review of literature. *Journal of Pharmacy And Bioallied Sciences*. 2015;7(2):S372-3.
8. Bouzaïdi K, Daghfous A, Fourati E, Kechaou I, Jabnoun F, Chtioui I. Eagle's syndrome. *Acta radiologica short reports*. 2013;2(5):204.
9. Jain S, Bansal A, Paul S, Prashar DV. Styloid-stylohyoid syndrome. *Annals of maxillofacial surgery*. 2012;2(1):66.
10. Bhuyan MAH, Afroza S, Nurullah M, Kafi MAH, Hossain MS. Tonsillo-styloidectomy for Eagle s syndrome: review of 20 cases. *Bangladesh Journal of Otorhinolaryngology*. 2012;18(2):149-55.
11. Thoenissen P, Bittermann G, Schmelzeisen R, Oshima T, Fretwurst T. Eagle's syndrome—A non-perceived differential diagnosis of temporomandibular disorder. *International journal of surgery case reports*. 2015;15:123-6.

